

 WageIndicator.org

Codebook
WageIndicator Garment
Supply Chain Database
2018

Maarten van Klaveren
Kea Tijdens

WageIndicator Foundation - www.wageindicator.org

WageIndicator started in 2001 to contribute to a more transparent labour market for workers and employers by publishing easily accessible information on a website. It collects, compares and shares labour market information through online and face-to-face surveys and desk research and publishes this on national websites with information on wages and labour law, and career advice, both for workers/employees and employers. The websites and related communication activities reach out to millions of people on a monthly basis. WageIndicator runs projects in the garment industries of Indonesia, Myanmar and Ethiopia, notably focusing on wages, working conditions and workers' rights.

The WageIndicator concept is owned by the independent, non-profit WageIndicator Foundation, established in 2003. Its Supervisory Board is chaired by the University of Amsterdam/AIAS-HSI and includes a representative from the Dutch Confederation of Trade Unions (FNV) and three independent members. The Foundation is assisted by world-renowned universities, trade unions and employers' organizations. It currently operates national websites in 92 countries. Its staff consists of some 100 specialists around the world. The Foundation has offices in Amsterdam (HQ), Ahmedabad, Bratislava, Buenos Aires, Cape Town, Islamabad and Venice.

Bibliographical information

Van Klaveren M, Tijdens KG (2018) Codebook WageIndicator Garment Supply Chain Database 2018. Amsterdam, WageIndicator Foundation, October.

This publication can be freely downloaded [here](#).

© WageIndicator Foundation, 2018

Address: P O Box 94025, 1090 GA Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Email: office@wageindicator.org

Table of content

1. Introduction	1
2. Variables	1
3. Number of observations and min/max values	2
4. Value labels	3

1. Introduction

This document contains the variable and value information of the 2018 WageIndicator Garment Supply Chain Database 2018. The report about the database is free downloadable and is called Van Klaveren, M., & Tijdens, K.G. (2018). [Mapping the Global Garment Supply Chain](#). WageIndicator Foundation, Amsterdam.

Please refer to the database as "Van Klaveren M, Tijdens KG (2018) WageIndicator Garment Supply Chain Database 2018. Amsterdam, Netherlands".

2. Variables

Variable	Label	Format
Factories_name	Name factory	A93
Parent_companies_name	Name parent company	A99
Country_parent	Country of parent	A12
Address_1_factory	<none>	A150
Address_2_factory	<none>	A79
Address_3_factory	<none>	A62
City_factory	City of factory	A25
Zip_Code_factory	<none>	F34
Province_State_factory	Province or state of factory	A31
countrycode	Country of factory (num)	F4
country_parent_num	country parent	F4
factory_parent_different	factory and parent are different	F4
Product_Categories_grp	Product group	F4
b1_Adidas	Adidas-Number of employees in factory	F4
b2_ASICS	ASICS-Number of employees in factory	F4
b3_ASOS	ASOS-Number of employees in factory	F4
b4_CandA	CandA-Number of employees in factory	F4
b5_Debenhams	Debenhams-Number of employees in factory	F4
b6_Esprit	Esprit-Number of employees in factory	F4
b7_GAP	GAP-Number of employees in factory	F4
b8_G_STAR	G_STAR-Number of employees in factory	F4
b9_HandM	HandM-Number of employees in factory	F4
b10_MandS	MandS-Number of employees in factory	F4
b11_NIKE	NIKE-Number of employees in factory	F4
b12_Pentland	Pentland-Number of employees in factory	F4
b13_Primark	Primark-Number of employees in factory	F4
b14_PUMA	PUMA-Number of employees in factory	F4
b15_Under_Armour	Under_Armour-Number of employees in factory	F4
b16_VF_Corp	VF_Corp-Number of employees in factory	F4
b17_Amer_Sports	Amer_Sports-Number of employees in factory	F4
b18_Bestseller	Bestseller-Number of employees in factory	F4
b19_KappAhl	KappAhl-Number of employees in factory	F4
b20_New_Balance	New_Balance-Number of employees in factory	F4
b21_Levi_Strauss	Levi_Strauss-Number of employees in factory	F4
b22_PVH	PVH-Number of employees in factory	F4
b23_Tesco	Tesco-Number of employees in factory	F4
b24_UNIQLO	UNIQLO-Number of employees in factory	F4
TOTAL_BRANDS	Total number of brands associated with factory	F4
employees_p_factory	Nr of workers per factory in 3 groups	F4
nonmbrs	Factories without employment data	F8.2
b1_Adidas_DICH	Factory supplies for Adidas	F4
b2_ASICS_DICH	Factory supplies for ASICS	F4

Variable	Label	Format
b3_ASOS_DICH	Factory supplies for ASOS	F4
b4_CandA_DICH	Factory supplies for CandA	F4
b5_Debenhams_DICH	Factory supplies for Debenhams	F4
b6_Esprit_DICH	Factory supplies for Esprit	F4
b7_GAP_DICH	Factory supplies for GAP	F4
b8_G_STAR_DICH	Factory supplies for G_STAR	F4
b9_HandM_DICH	Factory supplies for HandM	F4
b10_MandS_DICH	Factory supplies for MandS	F4
b11_NIKE_DICH	Factory supplies for NIKE	F4
b12_Pentland_DICH	Factory supplies for Pentland	F4
b13_Primark_DICH	Factory supplies for Primark	F4
b14_PUMA_DICH	Factory supplies for PUMA	F4
b15_Under_Armour_DICH	Factory supplies for Under_Armour	F4
b16_VF_Corp_DICH	Factory supplies for VF_Corp	F4
b17_Amer_Sports_DICH	Factory supplies for Amer_Sports	F4
b18_Bestseller_DICH	Factory supplies for Bestseller	F4
b19_KappAhl_DICH	Factory supplies for KappAhl	F4
b20_New_Balance_DICH	Factory supplies for New_Balance	F4
b21_Levi_Strauss_DICH	Factory supplies for Levi_Strauss	F4
b22_PVH_DICH	Factory supplies for PVH	F4
b23_Tesco_DICH	Factory supplies for Tesco	F4
b24_UNIQLO_DICH	Factory supplies for UNIQLO	F4
employees_p_factory_gt1000	Factory has more than 1000 employees	F8.2
ownership_grp	Ownership category	F4
TOTAL_BRANDS16	Total number of the 16 brands associated with factory	F4
TOTAL_BRANDS16_dich	Total number of the 16 brands associated with factory_binary	F4
fempeoyees_p_factory	Perc female workers per factory	F4
EPZ	Factory located in Export Processing Zone or similar	F4

3. Number of observations and min/max values

	N	Min	Max	Mean	S.Dev
countrycode	8110	50	818		
country_parent_num	8110	36	1043		
factory_parent_different	8110	0	1	0.53	0.499
Product_Categories_grp	8110	0	3	1.95	0.521
b1_Adidas	690	1	3	1.35	0.582
b2_ASICS	73	1	3	1.52	0.648
b3_ASOS	494	1	1	1.00	0.000
b4_CandA	755	1	3	1.20	0.425
b5_Debenhams	356	1	3	1.24	0.469
b6_Esprit	804	1	3	1.15	0.405
b7_GAP	777	1	3	1.43	0.566
b8_G_STAR	26	1	3	1.46	0.647
b9_HandM	1477	1	3	1.31	0.503
b10_MandS	518	1	3	1.40	0.529
b11_NIKE	330	1	3	1.74	0.705
b12_Pentland	118	1	3	1.31	0.515
b13_Primark	925	1	2	1.15	0.359
b14_PUMA	121	1	3	1.53	0.646
b15_Under_Armour	96	1	3	1.65	0.580
b16_VF_Corp	463	1	3	1.47	0.619
b17_Amer_Sports	63	0	0	0.00	0.000

	N	Min	Max	Mean	S.Dev
b18_Bestseller	259	0	0	0.00	0.000
b19_KappAhl	188	0	0	0.00	0.000
b20_New_Balance	103	0	0	0.00	0.000
b21_Levi_Strauss	418	0	0	0.00	0.000
b22_PVH	538	0	0	0.00	0.000
b23_Tesco	405	0	0	0.00	0.000
b24_UNIQLO	133	0	0	0.00	0.000
TOTAL_BRANDS	8110	1	7	1.25	0.629
employees_p_factory	8110	0	3	1.07	0.636
nonmbrs	8110	0	3	0.26	0.474
b1_Adidas_DICH	8110	0	1	0.09	0.279
b2_ASICS_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.094
b3_ASOS_DICH	8110	0	1	0.06	0.239
b4_CandA_DICH	8110	0	1	0.09	0.291
b5_Debenhams_DICH	8110	0	1	0.04	0.205
b6_Esprit_DICH	8110	0	1	0.10	0.299
b7_GAP_DICH	8110	0	1	0.10	0.294
b8_G_STAR_DICH	8110	0	1	0.00	0.057
b9_HandM_DICH	8110	0	1	0.18	0.386
b10_MandS_DICH	8110	0	1	0.06	0.245
b11_NIKE_DICH	8110	0	1	0.04	0.198
b12_Pentland_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.120
b13_Primark_DICH	8110	0	1	0.11	0.318
b14_PUMA_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.121
b15_Under_Armour_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.108
b16_VF_Corp_DICH	8110	0	1	0.06	0.232
b17_Amer_Sports_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.088
b18_Bestseller_DICH	8110	0	1	0.03	0.176
b19_KappAhl_DICH	8110	0	1	0.02	0.150
b20_New_Balance_DICH	8110	0	1	0.01	0.112
b21_Levi_Strauss_DICH	8110	0	1	0.05	0.221
b22_PVH_DICH	8110	0	1	0.07	0.249
b23_Tesco_DICH	8110	0	1	0.05	0.218
b24_UNIQLO_DICH	8110	0	1	0.02	0.127
employees_p_factory_gt1000	8110	0	1	0.20	0.399
ownership_grp	8110	1	4	1.76	0.790
TOTAL_BRANDS16	8110	0	6	0.99	0.596
TOTAL_BRANDS16_dich	8110	0	1	0.85	0.354
femployees_p_factory	2595	0	100	58.69	24.539
EPZ	8110	0	1	0.28	0.451

4. Value labels

Value		Label
countrycode	36	Australia
	50	Bangladesh
	52	Barbados
	56	Belgium
	92	Virgin Islands, British
	104	Myanmar
	116	Cambodia
	124	Canada
	144	Sri Lanka
	156	China

Value		Label
	158	Taiwan
	170	Colombia
	208	Denmark
	222	El Salvador
	231	Ethiopia
	246	Finland
	250	France
	276	Germany
	320	Guatemala
	340	Honduras
	344	Hong Kong
	356	India
	360	Indonesia
	372	Ireland
	376	Israel
	380	Italy
	392	Japan
	400	Jordan
	410	Korea Rep
	458	Malaysia
	484	Mexico
	504	Morocco
	512	Oman
	528	Netherlands
	586	Pakistan
	604	Peru
	608	Philippines
	620	Portugal
	642	Romania
	643	Russian Federation
	702	Singapore
	704	Vietnam
	724	Spain
	752	Sweden
	756	Switzerland
	764	Thailand
	784	United Arab Emirates
	788	Tunisia
	792	Turkey
	818	Egypt
	826	United Kingdom
	840	United States of America (USA)
	850	Virgin Islands (U.S.)
	1001	BD / IN
	1002	BD / UK
	1003	CN / CN
	1004	CN / HK
	1005	CN / IN
	1006	CN / KR
	1007	CN / US
	1008	HK / CA
	1009	HK / CN
	1010	HK / HK
	1011	HK / US
	1012	HN / HN
	1013	ID / HK
	1014	IN / IN
	1015	IN / TH
	1016	IT / CN

Value		Label
	1017	IT / FR
	1018	IT / IT
	1019	KR / RO
	1020	KR / US
	1021	LK / DE
	1022	LK / LK
	1023	LK / UK
	1024	LK / US
	1025	MX / MX
	1026	NL / IN
	1027	SG / ID
	1028	TH / TH
	1029	TR / EG
	1030	TW / CA
	1031	US / BD
	1032	US / CN
	1033	US / HK
	1034	US / TW
	1035	US / US
	1036	HK / UAE
	1037	CA / US / US
	1038	CN / CN / US
	1039	CN / US / IT
	1040	ID / US / HK
	1041	MX / MX / MX
	1042	PK / US / US
	1043	US / CN / US
country_parent_num	36	Australia
	50	Bangladesh
	52	Barbados
	56	Belgium
	92	Virgin Islands, British
	104	Myanmar
	116	Cambodia
	124	Canada
	144	Sri Lanka
	156	China
	158	Taiwan
	170	Colombia
	208	Denmark
	222	El Salvador
	231	Ethiopia
	246	Finland
	250	France
	276	Germany
	320	Guatemala
	340	Honduras
	344	Hong Kong
	356	India
	360	Indonesia
	372	Ireland
	376	Israel
	380	Italy
	392	Japan
	400	Jordan
	410	Korea Rep
	458	Malaysia
	484	Mexico
	504	Morocco

Value		Label
	512	Oman
	528	Netherlands
	586	Pakistan
	604	Peru
	608	Philippines
	620	Portugal
	642	Romania
	643	Russian Federation
	702	Singapore
	704	Vietnam
	724	Spain
	752	Sweden
	756	Switzerland
	764	Thailand
	784	United Arab Emirates
	788	Tunisia
	792	Turkey
	818	Egypt
	826	United Kingdom
	840	United States of America (USA)
	850	Virgin Islands (U.S.)
	1001	BD / IN
	1002	BD / UK
	1003	CN / CN
	1004	CN / HK
	1005	CN / IN
	1006	CN / KR
	1007	CN / US
	1008	HK / CA
	1009	HK / CN
	1010	HK / HK
	1011	HK / US
	1012	HN / HN
	1013	ID / HK
	1014	IN / IN
	1015	IN / TH
	1016	IT / CN
	1017	IT / FR
	1018	IT / IT
	1019	KR / RO
	1020	KR / US
	1021	LK / DE
	1022	LK / LK
	1023	LK / UK
	1024	LK / US
	1025	MX / MX
	1026	NL / IN
	1027	SG / ID
	1028	TH / TH
	1029	TR / EG
	1030	TW / CA
	1031	US / BD
	1032	US / CN
	1033	US / HK
	1034	US / TW
	1035	US / US
	1036	HK / UAE
	1037	CA / US / US
	1038	CN / CN / US

Value		Label
	1039	CN / US / IT
	1040	ID / US / HK
	1041	MX / MX / MX
	1042	PK / US / US
	1043	US / CN / US
factory_parent_different	0	no
	1	yes
Product_Categories_grp	0	rest
	1	Accessories
	2	Apparel
	3	Footwear
b1_Adidas	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b2_ASICS	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b3_ASOS	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b4_CandA	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b5_Debenhams	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b6_Esprit	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b7_GAP	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b8_G_STAR	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b9_HandM	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b10_MandS	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b11_NIKE	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b12_Pentland	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000

Value		Label
b13_Primark	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b14_PUMA	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b15_Under_Armour	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b16_VF_Corp	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b17_Amer_Sports	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b18_Bestseller	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b19_KappAhl	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b20_New_Balance	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b21_Levi_Strauss	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b22_PVH	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b23_Tesco	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b24_UNIQLO	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
employees_p_factory	0	no numbers
	1	1-1000
	2	1001-5000
	3	>5000
b1_Adidas_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b2_ASICS_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b3_ASOS_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b4_CandA_DICH	0	No

Value		Label
	1	Yes
b5_Debenhams_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b6_Esprit_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b7_GAP_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b8_G_STAR_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b9_HandM_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b10_MandS_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b11_NIKE_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b12_Pentland_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b13_Primark_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b14_PUMA_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b15_Under_Armour_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b16_VF_Corp_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b17_Amer_Sports_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b18_Bestseller_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b19_KappAhl_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b20_New_Balance_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b21_Levi_Strauss_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b22_PVH_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b23_Tesco_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
b24_UNIQLO_DICH	0	No
	1	Yes
employees_p_factory_gt1000	.00	No
	1.00	Yes
ownership_grp	1	Factory and owner are the same
	2	Factory owned by owner from same country
	3	Factory owned by foreign owner
	4	Factory owned by owners from multiple countries (joint ventures)
TOTAL_BRANDS16	0	Factory only for brand 17-24
TOTAL_BRANDS16_dich	0	Factory only for brand 17-24
	1	Factory associated with at least one of 16 brands